

SOCIAL SCIENCES

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ СОЦИАЛЬНЫХ КОНФЛИКТОВ В ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКИХ ОТНОШЕНИЯХ: ПРОБЛЕМЫ И СТРАТЕГИИ РЕШЕНИЯ

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FORMATION OF SOCIAL CONFLICTS IN HUMAN RELATIONS: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTION STRATEGIES

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В процессе развития общества в нём непрерывно происходят различные явления и процессы. Среди этих процессов особое место занимают социальные конфликты. Статья посвящена изучению специфики социальных конфликтов, которые отличаются пагубным воздействием на формирование человеческих отношений в обществе. В статье затронуты вопросы, связанные с причинами, источниками и типологией социальных конфликтов, а также раскрыты механизмы, методы и инструменты, направленные на совершенствование их управления в современной практике. В статье также сравнительным образом рассматриваются классические и современные теории социальных конфликтов. В отличие от аналогичных исследований, в статье рассматриваются научные исследования, проводимые в Азербайджане в области социальных конфликтов в настоящее время, определяются причины возникновения социальных конфликтов в современном азербайджанском обществе, критерии их классификации, а также дается интерпретация основных видов конфликтов, наиболее ярко проявляющихся на макро и микро уровнях. В конце статьи авторы предлагают эффективные предложения по урегулированию социальных конфликтов.

Целью исследования является изучение сущности, причин возникновения, особенностей социальных конфликтов, отличающихся негативным воздействием на формирование человеческих отношений в обществе, а также анализ подходов к их решению на научной основе.

В ходе исследования для изучения проблемы социального конфликта был использован комплексный методологический подход, включающий историко-методологический подход, социологический анализ, сравнительный анализ, системный подход, контент-анализ, теоретическое обобщение, аналитический анализ и общелогические методы.

В большинстве случаев социальные конфликты, различающиеся по своему влиянию на различные сферы общественной жизни, представляют особую актуальность, поскольку приводят к усилению отчаяния, пессимизма, эгоцентризма и, в конечном итоге, к моральной деградации в настроении и эмоциональной жизни людей, замедляют процесс их социализации, а в некоторых случаях и вовсе препятствуют ему.

Хотя первые всеобъемлющие концепции конфликта возникли на рубеже XIX–XX веков, но появление первых идей в этой области относится к I тысячелетию до н.э. Активное научное исследование конфликтов проходило в рамках классической социологии, а главный роль сыграли «пионеры» этого направления блестящие мыслители – О. Конт, К. Маркс, Г. Зиммель.

Основным источником социальных конфликтов является стратификация общества – его разделение на различные группы, страты, классы. Выявление причин конфликтов имеет большое значение для выявления проблемы, её предотвращения и конструктивного решения. Возникновение и развитие конфликтов связано с влиянием ряда факторов. К ним относятся: объективные, организационно-управленческие и социально-психологические.

Существует следующая классификация социальных конфликтов: межличностные конфликты; конфликты между индивидами и группами; внутригрупповые конфликты; внутриличностные конфликты; конфликты между малыми и большими социальными объединениями; этнонациональные конфликты; организационные конфликты; корпоративные конфликты.

Механизм регулирования конфликтов включает комплекс мер, направленных на минимизацию их деструктивных последствий и конструктивное разрешение. Методы управления социальными конфликтами включают стратегии, направленные на предотвращение конфликтов (происхождение), снижение эскалации, реинтеграцию и обеспечение устойчивого мира.

В современном Азербайджане исследования проблемы социальных конфликтов проводятся университетами, независимыми исследовательскими центрами и международными организациями, а причины, последствия и методы разрешения социальных, политических и этнических конфликтов занимают большое место в исследованиях. Местные ученые А. Велиев, Г. Ализаде, А. Гадиров, Э. Ахмедов и др. сыграли важную роль в развитии теорий социальных конфликтов в нашей стране.

Социальные конфликты в Азербайджане во многом обусловлены историческими и политическими претензиями со стороны бывшего СССР, а также этническим разнообразием и гендерными проблемами. На микросоциальном уровне среди социальных конфликтов в Азербайджане особый интерес представляют семейные конфликты и разводы. Последствия разводов сами по себе оказывают непосредственное негативное влияние на социальную стабильность в обществе, психологическое состояние детей и будущее развитие семейных отношений. На макросоциальном уровне среди социальных конфликтов в Азербайджане выделяется карабахский конфликт. Карабахский конфликт оказал серьезное влияние на политическое, экономическое, социальное и культурное развитие Азербайджанской Республики с конца XX века и стал долгосрочным источником напряженности в системе безопасности региона.

Правильное управление социальными конфликтами позволит избежать их глобальные последствия. Для предотвращения и управления социальными конфликтами необходим комплексный подход, охватывающий правовые, социальные, культурные и экономические аспекты, реализуемый при активном участии как государства, так и институтов гражданского общества.

ABSTRACT

As society develops, various types of events and processes continuously occur here. Among these processes, social conflicts stand out with their special weight. The article is devoted to the study of the specific features of social conflicts, which are distinguished by their harmful impact on the formation of human relations in society. The authors touched on issues related to the causes, sources, and typology of social conflicts in the article and clarified the mechanisms, methods, and tools aimed at improving their management in current practice. The article also examines classical and modern theories of social conflict in a comparative manner. Unlike similar studies, the article touches on scientific research conducted in Azerbaijan in the field of social conflicts at present, determines the causes of social conflicts in modern Azerbaijani society, classification the criteria, and gives an interpretation of the main types of conflicts that manifest themselves more prominently at the macro and micro levels. At the end of the article, the authors reflect on the rationalization proposals for the settlement of social conflicts.

The purpose of the study is to study the essence, causes of occurrence, specific features of social conflicts, which are distinguished by their harmful impact on the formation of human relations in society, and to analyze the approaches aimed at their solution on a scientific basis.

During the study, a complex methodological approach consisting of a historical-methodological approach, sociological analysis, comparative analysis, systematic approach, content analysis, theoretical generalization, analytical analysis, and general logical methods was used to investigate the problem of social conflict.

In most cases, social conflicts, which differ in their impact on various areas of social life, are of particular relevance, since they lead to more despair, pessimism, self-absorption and, ultimately, moral degradation in people's mood and emotional lives, and slow down the process of their socialization, and in some cases even hinder it altogether.

Although the first comprehensive concepts of conflict arose at the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries, the emergence of the first ideas in this field dates back to the 1st millennium BC. The active scientific research process of conflicts took place within the framework of classical sociology, and the role of the "pioneers" of this field was played mainly by brilliant thinkers - O. Comte, K. Marx, and G. Simmel.

The main source of social conflict is the stratification of society - its division into various groups, strata, and classes. Revealing the causes of conflicts is very important when identifying the problem, preventing it, and constructively solving it. The emergence and development of conflicts is associated with the influence of several factors. These include: objective, organizational management, and socio-psychological factors.

There is the following classification of social conflicts: interpersonal conflicts; conflicts between individuals and groups; intra-group conflicts; intra-personal conflicts; conflicts between small and large social associations; ethnic-national conflicts; organizational conflicts; corporate conflicts.

The mechanism of conflict regulation includes a complex of measures aimed at minimizing their destructive effects and constructively resolving them. Social conflict management methods include strategies aimed at preventing conflicts (provenance), reducing escalation, reintegration, and ensuring sustainable peace.

In modern Azerbaijan, research on the problem of social conflict is conducted by universities, independent research centers, and international organizations, and the causes, effects, and methods of resolving social, political, and ethnic conflicts occupy a large place in the research. Local scientists A. Valiyev, H. Alizadeh, A. Gadirov, E. Ahmadov, etc. have played a major role in the development of social conflict theories in our country.

Social conflicts in Azerbaijan are largely conditioned by historical and political claims from the former USSR, as well as ethnic diversity and gender problems. At the microsocial level, family conflicts and divorces are of particular interest among social conflicts in Azerbaijan. The consequences of divorces in themselves have a direct negative impact on social stability in society, the psychological state of children, and the future development of family relations. At the macrosocial level, the Karabakh conflict stands out among social conflicts in Azerbaijan. The Karabakh conflict has had a very serious impact on the political, economic, social, and cultural development of the Republic of Azerbaijan since the end of the 20th century and has become a long-term source of tension in the security system of the region.

If social conflicts are managed correctly, their total consequences can be avoided. In order to prevent and manage social conflicts, a complex approach covering legal, social, cultural, and economic aspects, implemented with the active participation of both state and civil society institutions, is required.

Ключевые слова: социальный конфликт, теории социальных конфликтов, источник конфликта, причины конфликта, механизм регулирования, методы управления, Азербайджан, семейные конфликты, разводы, этнический конфликт, Карабахский конфликт.

Keywords: social conflict, theories of social conflict, source of conflict, causes of conflict, regulation mechanism, management methods, Azerbaijan, family conflicts, divorces, ethnic conflict, Karabakh conflict.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study is to study the essence, causes of occurrence, specific features of social conflicts, which are distinguished by their harmful impact on the formation of human relations in society, and to analyze the approaches aimed at their solution on a scientific basis.

Methodology

The theoretical and methodological basis of the study is the existing views on social and political conflicts in the history of world philosophical and political thought. Numerous scientific research works published in our country and abroad on the problem of conflict were used as theoretical sources.

For the study, a complex methodological approach was used in the analysis of social conflicts. In order to trace the dynamics of the historical development of conflicts, a historical-methodological approach was used, in order to determine their structure and forms of manifestation in the social context, and sociological analysis was used. and when comparing with different countries and periods, comparative analysis methods were used. A systematic approach was taken as the basis in order to investigating the functional place of social conflicts in the social system of society and the mechanisms of interaction. At the same time, the content analysis method was used in the study of materials on social conflicts in scientific literature and mass media. The appropriate integration of methodological approaches ensured the objectivity and scientific substantiation of the research. In addition, theoretical generalization, analytical analysis, and general logical methods were also used.

Introduction

As society develops, various types of events and processes continuously occur here. Among these processes, social conflicts stand out and differ in their specific gravity, frequency of development, and diversity. Social conflicts have always accompanied the entire history of humanity with their consequences of varying severity. In certain historical periods of human history,

these conflicts did not remain only in one sphere of society, but sometimes covered entire countries and peoples. Even now, conflicts have become an integral part of our daily lives. Even sometimes, even in conditions of cooperation and agreement, the existence of a conflict situation emerges as an undeniable reality.

Conflicts in the social sphere mainly cover conflicts occurring at the levels of social life. However, a conflict that arises in any area of the social sphere can also contain the characteristics of other conflicts.

Conflicts are usually evaluated as situations that should be avoided. At the heart of any conflict is the opposing positions of the parties, for some reason or the mismatch of means and goals or interests, desires, in the current circumstances.

Unfortunately, social conflicts are often accompanied by disputes, psycho-emotional tension, aggression, threats, and hostility. This leads to hopelessness, pessimism, self-absorption, and ultimately moral degradation in people's mood and emotional life, slowing down their socialization process, and in some cases, completely preventing it. It is from this perspective that the study of social conflicts, which differ in their impact on various areas of society, is of particular relevance today.

The abundance of conflicts in society in modern times makes the study of their essence, typology, dynamics, functions, and management an inevitable reality. In this regard, the analysis and study of conflicts is also of great importance for the Azerbaijani society, which is constantly renewing itself based on democratic development trends.

Social conflicts have been considered an undesirable phenomenon in society for many years. Of course, since each era has its characteristics, people's views and approaches to various objects have also been different.

It is well known to us from our recent past that conflicts were not studied in depth during the Soviet period. It was believed that the socialist society was supposedly a perfect, ideal society, free from contradictions, developing harmoniously. The contradictions existing in society were covered up, and, ultimately, they

became a source of tension without finding a solution. After the collapse of the Soviet Union, social conflicts that manifested themselves in various spheres of society in the newly established republics in the national, religious, ideological, ethnic, etc. forms arose precisely from these contradictions.

In modern times, in-depth study and research of both the causes of social conflicts and methods of their elimination have become widespread both in the world and in our country after gaining its state independence. This factor plays an important role in the fundamental solution of conflicts occurring in society. The most important issue facing Azerbaijani society today is learning to live with conflicts and deeply mastering the habits and technologies of managing them effectively.

Theoretical Approaches to the Concept of Social Conflict

The history of thought regarding conflicts dates back to the distant past, and the traditions of the emergence of conflictological ideas have a centuries-old history. Although the first comprehensive concepts of conflict emerged at the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries, in previous centuries, the greatest minds of humanity had also shared their views and opinions on the nature of this phenomenon, as well as on ways to prevent and resolve conflicts, and had put forward their ideas and teachings. [4, p. 83]

In various historical periods, thinkers have, in one way or another, touched upon the causes of conflicts, emphasizing such qualities that have always existed among individuals in society as interests, desires, demands, needs, benefits, envy, jealousy, and others.

The comprehension and interpretation of the phenomenon of conflict initially began within the framework of philosophy, which served as the foundation for all socio-political sciences, and was later developed in a deeper form and content by other disciplines. Looking back at history, it becomes clear that attempts to study conflicts in a systematic way date back to the first millennium BC. [8, p. 63] It was during this period that the accumulated experience began to be analyzed in a generalized manner.

In the early period, the study of conflicts was mostly abstract. Initially, attempts were made to examine conflicts primarily between individual social groups, state power, and society. Later on, the scope expanded to include the study of economic, social-class, political, interethnic, and intra-group conflicts. [14, p. 18]

In the philosophical investigation of conflict, the works of ancient philosophers such as the Greek thinkers Epicurus, Heraclitus, Plato, Democritus, Aristotle, the Chinese philosopher Confucius, and other ancient scholars held particular significance. The conceptual ideas developed by these thinkers, reflecting contradictions, as well as teachings about the struggle between opposing sides, were very important. Their studies continue to form the moral foundation of modern conflictology.

Among these philosophers, Aristotle, in his work *Politics*, investigated the primary causes of conflicts in

society, attributing them mainly to the fact that members of society possessed different properties. [18, p. 25]

Democritus's social-ethical and legal ideas also attracted great interest. He noted that "envy leads to hostility, resulting in harm inflicted on one another; laws necessarily put an end to such arbitrariness and do not allow everyone to live as they wish." [8, p. 81]

The ancient Chinese thinker Confucius tried to prove with his ideas that hatred and stubbornness, as well as conflicts, primarily create inequality and uniqueness in people. He saw the root of the conflict in the fact that society consists of "noble people" and ordinary "ordinary" people. In other words, if for noble people the basis of society consists of certain rules and laws, then ordinary people seek this basis in their benefit. [3, p. 25]

In later periods, Aurelius Augustine, Thomas Aquinas, Niccolo Machiavelli, and Francis Bacon put forward valuable ideas about the nature of the contradictions occurring in society, the positive or negative impact of these contradictions on the life of society.

Theorists of social Darwinism (H. Spencer, W. Sumner, and others) also made several contributions to the field of studying conflicts. They tried to transfer the principles of natural selection from biology to social knowledge, explaining this by the struggle of individuals and groups for the survival of society, achieving balance within society, and ensuring the process of social development.

The active scientific research process of conflicts took place within the framework of classical sociology, which, after separating from philosophy, became an independent scientific field. The role of the "pioneers" of this field was played mainly by brilliant thinkers - O. Comte, K. Marx, G. Simmel. [14, p. 24]

The position of Marxism on social conflicts was closely connected with its worldview based on class societies and historical materialism. According to Marxism, social conflicts arise from the class structure of society and inequality in the distribution of the means of production. [5, p. 22]

According to Marx, under certain conditions, hidden class interests turn into explicit interests, which leads to the division of society into two classes united in revolutionary conflict. [7, p. 240] The aforementioned idea of Marx was the main premise for criticizing his concept of conflict. It would not be correct to say that conflicts consist only of class conflicts. This simplifies the real essence of the matter.

It should be noted that the term "sociology of conflict" was first introduced into scientific literature by G. Simmel. G. Simmel considered conflict as a form of socialization. In his work "Social Differentiation", he clarified the nature of conflict and presented it as a contradiction between the parties fighting each other. [16, p. 14]

G. Simmel believed that each conflict within society is inevitable and inevitable. It is from this perspective that he emphasized that conflict is a universal phenomenon, that conflict is not just a clash of interests, but something more productive - that is, it arises based on people's instincts. [6, p. 38]

K. Boulding “*General Conflict Theory*”, R. Dahrendorf “*Conflict Model of Society*”, L. Kozer “*Positive Functional Conflict*” created fundamental theories that gave a significant impetus to the development of the science of conflictology. [6, p. 45]

The ideas of the German researcher Ralf Dahrendorf have made a great contribution to the development of the science of conflictology in general. In his work “*Classes and Class Conflict in Industrial Society*”, he argues that the occurrence of conflicts is a natural phenomenon. The absence of conflict at all is an anomaly for society. In his opinion, conflict allows us to control social problems. R. Dahrendorf, in his work “*Modern Social Conflict*,” touches on the problem of political conflict in more depth and notes that the basis of conflict in society is political confrontation between social groups. [7, p. 240]

Along with Western countries, one of the countries where conflictology has developed very widely is Russia. The 1990s of the 20th century is considered to be the period when conflictology, which was restricted during the USSR period, was formed as an independent scientific field in the post-Soviet space, including Russia, and rapidly developed. The political, social, and ethnic contradictions that arose after the collapse of the USSR increased interest in this field and opened the way for new research directions. During the USSR, studies on conflict were limited by ideological reasons. Conflict was presented as a phenomenon inherent in capitalist societies. With the liberalization of the political system in the 1990s, a neutral and scientific approach to conflict became possible. Conflictology was integrated with psychology, sociology, political science, and law. Against the background of serious transformations taking place in society, the study of conflicts emerged as a practical need, as ethnic conflicts, political confrontations, and social changes increased interest in this field. [3, p. 46]

Since this period, Russian researchers have attached special importance to the problem of conflict and conducted numerous studies. The contributions to science in this field of the famous Russian conflictologist, A. Dmitriyev and V. Kudryatsev, who are considered the founders of conflictology in Russia, as well as other researchers, V. Shalenko, Y. Zaprudsky, A. Antsupov, M. Vasilyev, A. Dorynin, and P. Tsygankov, are undeniable.

The Russian conflictologists mentioned above conducted research in the following areas: Ethnic and national conflicts (Chechnya, Dagestan, the Caucasus region); Political and ideological conflicts (new ideological platforms that emerged after the collapse of the USSR); Social conflicts arising from economic interests; Management of organizational and corporate conflicts; Psychological aspects of personal and intergroup conflicts. [4, p. 87]

The analysis of the nature of the conflict and theoretical and methodological approaches shows that both European and American scholars, as well as Russian conflictologists, approached the concept of conflict from different aspects, from different angles, and although in some cases there was some convergence on certain issues, in the end they did not show a common

position on it. More specifically, one group of researchers considered social conflict as a psychological factor, another group as a sociological one, interpreting it as a tension between individuals, small groups, as well as large social groups within any state.

The most important of the main points that caught our attention when reviewing the research conducted on social conflicts to date is the lack of a single definition of this complex, multi-spectrum phenomenon. Thus, each researcher who studies social conflict tries to define it following the subject of the field he represents (for example, a pedagogue considers its impact on the educational process, a psychologist considers its psychological characteristics, a lawyer considers its impact on the social structure of the state, the legal system, a political scientist considers its opportunities to influence the political system of society, political power, and a sociologist considers its negative and positive role in the management of society as a whole), as a result, its other specific characteristics are ignored, and it is interpreted according to a specific parameter.

Recent scientific research and publications on social conflicts

In recent decades, social conflicts have increased sharply not only in developing countries, but also in developed societies. Political polarization, social inequality, ethnic and religious conflicts, and technological transformation lead to the emergence of new types of social tensions.

Modern approaches to the problem of social conflicts at the global level are mainly distinguished by their multi-spectrum. Among these approaches, it is possible to distinguish studies on political polarization and ideological conflicts, approaches based on the development of the digital environment and radicalism, psychological aspects of social conflicts, and the direction of identity identification. [6, p.38]

Research conducted in recent years shows that in leading countries in the world - especially in the USA and European countries- political polarization has become the main factor of social fragmentation in society. The study “Towards global equity in political polarization research”, published in 2025, revealed the existing regional inequality in this area. [8, p. 63] At the same time, studies conducted in the Middle East demonstrate the transition of ideological conflicts into violent confrontations.

Recent studies prove that social media platforms have become a leading tool for the spread of extremist ideologies among young people in connection with the transition to the information society. A 2025 report by The Guardian newspaper notes that right-wing extremists conduct campaigns aimed at young audiences on gaming platforms such as Discord and Twitch with the aim of radicalization. The result of these campaigns, in many cases, leads to problems that have serious consequences for society (reactionaries settled in the country suffer more from this). [12, p. 237]

Psychological studies by the University of Oxford in the UK have shown that in recent times, individuals fully identify themselves with a certain group that has great influence and a dominant position in the sphere in

which they operate ("identity fusion"), which strengthens conflict-prone behavior in society. The tolerance displayed by these individuals, however, can reduce the potential for real conflict in this case. [16, p. 14]

Source, causes, and classification of social conflicts

Social conflict means the transformation of the discontent of opposing parties - people, social groups, or social forces, arising on the basis of social inequality, into a contradiction in the ideological plane, a "cold" confrontation, and a physical collision for the sake of interests. [17, p. 90]

The main source of social conflict is the stratification of society - its division into various groups, strata, and classes. The contradiction between the productive forces and the relations of production in society allows the emergence of social conflicts, which manifest themselves in the struggle between social strata, groups, classes; in the conflict between generations (in the family, in the organization); in the struggle between ethnic groups; in the activities of various religious communities that contradict each other; in the struggle between the bearers of newly emerged customs and traditions and the supporters of old customs and traditions. [16, p. 33]

People always react harshly to changes in socio-economic conditions, based on their interests. Naturally, the failure to satisfy any demand results in conflict. Differences in income levels, the almost non-existence of the middle class, and instability in economic, social, and political development lead to the emergence of conflicts. This manifests itself both between people and at the level of organizations and society.

Revealing the causes of conflicts is very important in identifying the problem, its prevention, and a constructive solution. It is impossible to exert a regulatory influence on it without knowing the driving forces of the conflict. It is impossible to influence the natural course of the conflict based on descriptive models alone.

The emergence and development of conflicts are associated with the influence of several factors. These include: objective, organizational management, and socio-psychological factors. The first two groups of factors are objective. The third and fourth factors are considered subjective factors. [2, p. 161]

Objective and subjective causes of conflicts

Understanding the objective-subjective causes of conflicts is very important in finding ways to prevent interpersonal conflicts, in choosing the optimal strategy of people's behavior during typical conflicts.

An example of objective causes of conflicts is the conditions that lead to the clash of interests, ideas, and views of people during their social relations. Objective causes lead to the emergence of pre-conflict conditions. It plays the role of an objective component of the pre-conflict conditions. [14, p. 24]

Subjective causes of conflicts are mainly related to the individual psychological characteristics of the opponents. They choose the conflict solution to the objectively contradictory conditions that have arisen. A

person does not agree to a compromise solution to the problem in any way, does not go to court, does not try to avoid conflict, and does not try to resolve the arising contradiction in conditions of mutual understanding. On the contrary, he prefers the strategy of counteraction. Practically in any pre-conflict situation, there are several conflict or non-conflict solutions and options for the conflict. The reasons for a person's choice of the conflict option are, in principle, subjective. [2, p. 165]

The results of the conducted social and socio-psychological studies allow us to identify the following main causes of social conflicts:

➤ Socio-economic reasons - conflicts arise in modern society as a manifestation and derivative of objective socio-economic contradictions.

➤ Socio-psychological reasons are formed based on the needs, goals of activity, and behavior of individual people.

➤ Socio-demographic reasons - diversity in goals and behavioral motives of people based on their age and gender. [3, p. 87]

In general, from a sociological point of view, 4 groups of reasons can be considered that determine the occurrence of social conflicts:

1. Individual differences in the upbringing of people;
2. Communicative errors;
3. Cultural contradictions;
4. Organization (differences between the general and individual goals of groups). [7, p. 249]

Typology of social conflicts

Since the typification or systematization of social conflicts is one of the most complex and difficult issues of the problem under study, there are many considerations and points of view in the scientific literature that differ from each other to a greater or lesser extent.

The classification of conflicts is important because it allows you to find specific forms of expression and evaluate possible options for their resolution. The main purpose of the classification is to determine the boundaries in the multitude of conflicts that are the object of research, to separate the most important structural elements from them. It is very difficult to conduct a complete classification of conflicts. The main problem in conducting a classification of conflicts is related to their complexity and limited study.

Researchers offer different approaches to classifying conflicts. For example, sociologists pay more attention to the macro or micro levels, socio-economic, national-ethnic, and political forms of conflicts. Lawyers distinguish between intra-system and extra-system conflicts and their areas of expression, including family-domestic, cultural, social-labor, as well as economic, financial, and property conflicts arising in a market economy. Management conflictology also has its approach. Here, it is necessary to more clearly imagine the main elements of conflicts, the diversity of methods of their expression, development, and management, etc. [17, p. 99]

Social conflicts can be distinguished on various grounds. Conflicts are mostly assessed based on the following criteria:

- ❖ parties to the conflict, limitation of the needs leading to the conflict;
- ❖ direction, orientation of the conflict;
- ❖ time limits of the conflict. [14, p. 15]

Types of social conflicts. The main types of conflicts are determined depending on the criterion taken as the basis of the classification. When the characteristics of the parties are taken as the basis of social conflicts, the following conflicts can be distinguished:

- interpersonal conflicts;
- conflicts between the individual and the group;
- intra-group conflicts;
- intra-personal conflicts;
- conflicts between small and large social associations;
- ethnic-national conflicts;
- organizational conflicts;
- corporate conflicts. [7, p. 241]

Mechanisms and management methods for regulating social conflicts

The mechanism for regulating conflicts includes a set of measures aimed at minimizing their destructive effects and constructively resolving them. The concepts formed in the field of conflict regulation in modern times are based more on theoretical foundations and try to explain the impact of various social, political, cultural, and economic factors on this process in a comprehensive way. These concepts, in addition to assessing the effectiveness of traditional conflict resolution methods, offer new methods and approaches aimed at adapting them to modern conditions. The multifaceted nature of conflicts, accordingly, necessitates differentiation of approaches in the process of their regulation.

The process of conflict regulation is multifaceted and complex, and the goal of this process can be aimed at stopping, resolving, or transforming (changing) the conflict. Different conceptual explanations of these goals give rise to the consideration of the possibilities of applying several methodological approaches to conflict regulation. [17, p. 15]

Existing theories not only identify the causes of conflict but also typify possible outcomes of negotiations. In this case, such important factors as the interests of the parties, the level of mutual trust, the balance of power, and the role of external actors are taken into account. Researchers offer specific steps and strategies for conducting constructive negotiations. These recommendations include: effective communication, the involvement of mediators, the alignment of interests, the reduction of emotional tension, and the establishment of long-term cooperation. [17, p. 16]

Methods of social conflict management

Social conflict management methods include strategies aimed at preventing conflicts (prevention), reducing escalation, reintegration, and ensuring sustainable peace. In general, social conflict management methods are extremely diverse. They can be divided into four groups:

- 1) methods of studying and assessing the personality (observation, survey, test); social-psychological in groups
- 2) methods of studying and assessing phenomena (observation, survey, sociometric method);
- 3) method of conflict analysis and diagnostics (observation, survey, analysis of the results of activities);
- 4) methods of conflict management (structural methods, cartographic methods). [8, p. 64]

In connection with the above situations, the methods of resolving them are also quite diverse. Examples of them are:

- Destruction (prevention) of one or both parties to the conflict;
- Elimination of the object of the conflict;
- Change in the position of one or both parties to the conflict;
- The emergence of a third party to the conflict, which will resolve it by force;
- Attempts by the parties to resolve the conflict with the help of the court or third parties;
- Use of negotiations and public diplomacy as one of the methods of conflict resolution. [17, p. 92]

A number of universal principles of managing social conflicts are known. First, one can distinguish two interconnected lines of reduction (two areas) of the conflict, which depend on the nature of the perception of the opponent, and secondly, on the nature of the competition. In addition to the general principles of conflict management, there are a number of specific rules and recommendations for the regulation or resolution of conflicts. These are the rules for managing social conflicts, which are often closely related to each other. [16, p. 16]

In the conditions of new changing realities, there is a serious need to form a more optimal, new theoretical and applied toolkit for the analysis and regulation of social conflicts. In this regard, the implementation of more serious research work towards the creation of a universal social conflict theory that will allow explaining conflict situations in society has emerged as an inevitable necessity in our rapidly changing world.

When approaching the issue from this context, the study of social conflicts and methods of their resolution, the importance of analyzing and studying conflicts, their positive and negative sides, and the assessment of their role in resolving conflicts are very important and relevant. In cases where the conflict gets out of control, it will inevitably give negative forms and consequences in society. If conflicts are not managed properly, they can lead to the deterioration of human relations, the socio-psychological environment in society, the loss of people's positions, and very large cataclysms. The longer the conflict lasts, the less chance the losing party has of achieving successful outcomes. In long-term conflicts, the business nature of the conflict decreases, while its emotional and personal nature increases. In a long-term struggle, the claims and insults made during the conflict become rude, so the object falls into the background. This acts as a factor that leads to tension, pessimism, divorces, and suicides in society, in labor collectives, in families, and within the individual.

Consequently, modern conflict resolution concepts are a dynamically developing field both theoretically and practically. Globalization, the impact of information technologies, transnational security challenges, and new geopolitical realities change the nature of conflicts, as well as renew the means and methods of their resolution. Therefore, it is necessary for specialists working in the field of conflict resolution to master multidisciplinary approaches and develop complex analysis skills.

Social conflicts in Azerbaijan: theoretical foundations and regulatory mechanisms

Research on the problem of social conflict in modern Azerbaijan is conducted by universities, independent research centers, and international organizations. Another important point is that social conflict theories in our country are developed mainly within the framework of sociology, philosophy, and political sciences; they are developed with different approaches, and the integration of theory and practice in this area is constantly expanding. The causes, effects, and methods of resolving social, political, and ethnic conflicts occupy a wide place in the research conducted. However, there is still a need to increase the number and quality of research in terms of multidisciplinary analysis of conflicts and the application of modern methods.

A number of local scientists have played an important role in the formation and development of social conflict theories in our country. Their research is aimed at clarifying the essence, causes, and solutions of social conflicts from both theoretical and applied perspectives. Among these scientists, A. Valiyev, H. Alizadeh, A. It is worth mentioning the names of Gadirov, E. Ahmadov, J. Naghiyev, H. Abbasli, U. Shiraliyev, Y. Aliyeva, and R. Abbasbeyli. Local specialists relied on both classical conflict theories (Marxism, structural-functionalism, symbolic interactionism, etc.) and approaches based on the problems of transition, post-conflict society, ethnic relations, and social justice in the local context. Currently, in our country, which is experiencing a post-conflict period, existing research is more focused in this direction.

Regarding new directions in the field of social conflict research in Azerbaijan, it can be said that scientific research in this field has been conducted and developed in recent years both individually by the above-mentioned authors representing various scientific fields, as well as through various academic publications and scientific-practical conferences. In particular, after the successful resolution of the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict, which left an indelible mark on the modern history of Azerbaijan, social research aimed at ensuring reintegration and normalizing socio-psychological relations in our society has become more widespread.

It should be specially noted here that scientific conferences such as the “2nd International Conference on Social Work & Social Research” and the “International Conference on Peace, Conflict and Justice” held in the capital of Azerbaijan, Baku, in 2025 have expanded scientific discussions in the field of social conflicts. At these events, the speeches of Azerbaijani scientists on the issues of social inequality, reintegration of internally displaced persons, and psychosocial adaptation in the post-conflict period attracted special attention. In the dissertation submitted by Azerbaijani researcher Firuz Suleymanov in 2025, the social and environmental consequences of the Karabakh conflict were analyzed, especially in the context of water security and land use. [9, p. 54]

Social conflicts are inevitable events during the development of every society. Against the backdrop of the complex social transformations taking place in Azerbaijan in recent times, social conflicts of various levels and forms are becoming more pronounced. The spectrum of social conflicts in our republic is wide and closely related to historical and political conditions. These conflicts are largely conditioned by historical and political claims left over from the former USSR period, as well as factors such as ethnic diversity, gender issues, ultra-Europeanization, urbanization, and migration.

The main types of social conflicts occurring in Azerbaijan in modern times include the following:

- ❖ **Socio-economic conflicts** (issues such as low wages, price increases, inflation, unemployment, insufficient social security, etc., form the basis of these conflicts);
- ❖ **Regional and center-periphery conflicts** (uneven organization of social services in the regions and dissatisfaction with improper management can be cited as examples of these conflicts);
- ❖ **Conflicts related to the environment and ecological problems** (small-scale conflicts related to the shortage of natural resources and damage to them can be cited as examples);
- ❖ **Tensions related to youth and the education sector** (protest-based social media posts about youth unemployment, students' living conditions, and the quality of education are related to this conflict);
- ❖ **Gender-based social conflicts** (active public discussions and protests about domestic violence, women's rights, and women's limited opportunities in the labor market are the reasons for this). [10, p. 60]

Currently, social conflicts existing in contemporary Azerbaijani society can be grouped according to the following classification criteria: [15, p. 74]

Scheme 1.

Classification and nature of conflicts

Type of Conflict	Parties	Level	Nature
Economic	Worker – Employer	Local	Structural
Ecological	Local Population – Government Authorities	Regional	Normative Ecological
Cultural-Gender	Woman – Patriarchal System	Local–National	Ideological-Social
Political	Citizen – Government	Nationwide	nstitutional

The list of global problems experienced in the world in the 21st century is constantly expanding. Among the problems of conflict and tension, global warming, pandemics, international migration, etc., according to the generally accepted opinion, one of the areas, even the first, that is exposed to a deep crisis is the family institution.

At the microsocal level, family conflicts and divorces attract special attention among social conflicts in Azerbaijan. Currently, the traditional family model is experiencing a crisis all over the world. In this regard, the search for answers to questions related to the causes of the crisis in various societies, the processes of decline of family values, their depth, ways out, etc., has become intensive. The complexity of the problem is also because currently the family institution is paradoxically exposed to total influence and great pressure from almost all important subsystems of society - culture, information, economy, politics, health, science, education, etc. [19, p. 17]

In 2021, at the initiative of the State Committee for Family, Women and Children's Issues of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the Center for Social Research carried out a large-scale sociological survey project for the first time in the history of the country, to study the dynamics and transformation of intra-family relations, including conflict situations, family values, and the interaction and connection in the modern Azerbaijani family, where the above-mentioned influences do not bypass it, and to systematically study the general picture in family issues. The presented analytical report reflects the results of studying the family institution and family values in Azerbaijani society, public opinion's perceptions of reality, expectations, and current state and prospects of family development trends in general, by applying modern approaches in the aspect of sociological research of the family. The results were summarized by conducting a statistical quantitative and qualitative analysis of the respondents' responses on the problems faced by families in our country, their causes, and ways to overcome them. [19, p. 18]

As a result of the research, it became clear that a number of problems are clearly emerging in the current Azerbaijani family, leading to serious intra-family social tension and social crisis. Among them, intra-family conflicts arising from a variety of socio-economic and cultural reasons, as well as improperly established marital relations and division of roles and responsibilities, act as a threat to social stability in society and are one of the main sources of social tension. [19, p. 18] According to current statistics, divorces, which show a significant increase every year, have the status of the main problem of the modern Azerbaijani family, arising from moral and psychological reasons.

If we look at the statistics of the last four years, we will see that in general, 14,628 divorce cases were registered in Azerbaijan in 2020, 17,191 in 2021, 15,983 in 2022, 21,688 in 2023, and 21,384 in 2024. On the other hand, the analysis shows that divorces are constantly increasing not only among young families, but also among people over 50 years of age. [20]

Our observations give reason to say that social, economic, and psychological factors are behind the collapse of long-term marriages. The consequences of divorces themselves have a direct negative impact on social stability in society, the psychological state of children, and the future development of family relationships.

In Azerbaijani society, as in the rest of the world, the increase in the economic independence of individuals has radically changed the principles of society's approach to divorce. In traditional Azerbaijani families, if in previous times the main value was considered to be preserving the family as the cornerstone of national and spiritual values, now individual happiness has come to the fore, pushing other issues into the background. In other words, people no longer feel a social and economic obligation to continue mutual relations. [19, p. 18]

Also, problems that have not been resolved for many years lead to the decision to divorce between couples. According to sociologists, as age increases, attention to the quality of life and personal well-being also increases; some couples choose different lifestyles, which in turn similarly affects the continuity of mutual relations. According to another conclusion of sociologists, the fact that long-term marriages end in divorce is an adequate result of individual and social changes. Economic independence, weakening of social taboos, and orientation towards personal happiness act as the main factors of this process. This process is called the "Gray" divorce phenomenon in the world and has become an increasingly growing trend. [19, p. 19]

At the macrosocial level, the Karabakh conflict stands out among the social conflicts in Azerbaijan. One of the social conflicts that has manifested itself prominently in Azerbaijani society is the fact that our people have been subjected to great deprivations and losses for many years.

Currently, a number of legal and institutional mechanisms have been formed by the state in order to regulate, eliminate, and minimize social conflicts existing in Azerbaijani society, and this activity is continuously developed on an upward line. These mechanisms include:

- Formation and development of the regulatory and legal framework (improving the constitution, labor and administrative legislation, laws on human rights, and in some cases adopting new ones);
- Formation of alternative conflict resolution institutions (mediation institution, ombudsman institution);
- Development and implementation of state programs (development of the social security system, projects related to youth employment) to eliminate conflicts;
- Support by the state for the activities of NGOs and civil society institutions (activities related to the promotion of social peace and dialogue). [9, p. 54]

The social conflicts existing in Azerbaijan are complex and multifaceted. To prevent and manage these conflicts, individual approaches are needed not only at the legal level, but also in social, psychological, and institutional directions. Early identification of conflict risks, formation and development of a culture of

dialogue, as well as expansion of inclusive and tolerant governance, are important in this area to ensure sustainable social stability.

Conclusions and suggestions

Preliminary analyses also show that conflict, in the broad sense of the word, acts as one of the possible consequences of human activity in one or another area. It manifests itself in various spheres of society - from everyday life, family to state, international relations. It is impossible to completely resolve or eliminate conflicts. As long as there are societies and human communities with different characteristics, the existence of conflicts is inevitable from this point of view. However, by managing conflicts with certain methods, means and means, it is possible to weaken, minimize their harmful consequences, and have a positive impact on them. This idea is valid both in society and in the regulation of conflicts occurring within a specific social institution and social group.

If social conflicts are managed correctly, their total consequences can be avoided. A comprehensive approach is required to prevent and manage social conflicts. This approach should cover legal, social, cultural, and economic aspects and should be implemented with the active participation of both state and civil society institutions. For the effective management of social conflicts in Azerbaijan, both the improvement of the national legislative framework and the expansion of public dialogue and awareness-raising measures are of great importance.

The following proposals have been put forward to regulate social conflicts that disrupt human relations in society:

1. Promotion of dialogue and opening of communication channels.
2. Expansion of mediation opportunities.
3. Development of awareness-raising and special education programs.
4. Improvement of the legislative framework and legal mechanisms to ensure social justice and prevent violations of the law.
5. Promotion of intercultural dialogue and intergroup cooperation.
6. Formation of an educational base aimed at developing problem-solving skills in higher education institutions.

These measures can help prevent the emergence of social conflicts and resolve existing problems peacefully. In addition, individual strategies should be developed that are appropriate to the specific conflict and the characteristics of the society.

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